

Chapter 1. Setting the Scene^{1,2}

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¹This is the final text version of Chapter 1 from the Assessment Report on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species. A laid-out version of the full assessment report will be made available in the coming months.

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List of supplementary materials

S1.1 List of knowledge gaps identified in the IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species

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The knowledge gaps presented below were assembled from the knowledge gaps identified in the individual chapters. They are organized thematically rather than by chapter, because many knowledge gaps have implications for multiple chapters. The gaps are identified based on best information from literature review and experts' knowledge as missing from the literature and other appropriate sources. The chapter section where the knowledge gap was identified is referenced in brackets.

Knowledge gaps regarding quantity and quality of data and information available, and ability to access the data

- For all wild species and uses, amount and availability of data can be improved, particularly at spatial scales comparable to the scales of use and of management. However, there are some particularly large gaps in some types of data and information, including:
 - o The roles of different taxonomic groups in the contributions of nature to people {3.2.4, 3.5, 4.6};
 - o How nature's contributions influence human well-being, particularly with regard to gender equality;
 - o How the status of species and nature's contributions to people are linked to specific ecosystem functions {3.5, 3.6.2.2};
 - o Consistent differentiation between wild and non-wild species across different practices, in particular fishing and logging {3.3.1, 3.3.4.};
 - o On the number of species used across different regions, particularly in gathering and non-extractive practices, and for insects and plants used for food, and for fungi and micro-organisms, where even taxonomic identification is incomplete {3.2};
 - o Guidance to improve consistency among worldwide and regional databases to quantify the harvest and uses of wild species {3.2.1.5};
 - o Databases containing information on policies adopted by different levels of governance intended to achieve or maintain sustainability of uses {3.2.1};
 - o Databases on extent of enforcement/implementation of policies that have been adopted by governance processes; including types of measures adopted, extent of monitoring of status and uses, consultation processes instituted, etc. {3.2.1};
 - o Information on sources, quality assurance, safety and efficacy of traditional medicine {3.5}.
- There is a lack of in-depth studies of ecosystem resilience in all systems, and how resilience is affected by uses, particularly uses other than fishing {4.5}.
- There is a lack of long-term temporal and spatial studies, particularly for non-fishing practices {4.5}.
- A knowledge gap exists on the impacts of health-oriented uses of wild species, particularly plants, on human community health {3.3.1.4.2, 3.3.2.2.2, 3.3.5.2.2}.

- Strengthen consistency, breadth, and depth of documentation of threats and use & trade classification schemes in the International Union for Conservation of Nature Red List of Threatened Species assessments {3.2.1, 3.2.2}.
- Lack of guidance on how to extract robust indicators and their uncertainties at various temporal and spatial scales (including national) from the databases and information available {3.2.1}. This gap is particularly great for gathering, non-extractive practices, and, in some parts of the world, logging {3.3, 3.3.2, 3.3.4, 3.3.5}.
- Few indicators have been developed for all uses by indigenous peoples and local communities {3.2.2.1}, for methods which combine information from multiple knowledge systems {3.2}, and particularly to address the weak documentation of subsistence and indigenous economies at all scales, including economic aspects of cultural, spiritual and social uses of wild species {3.2}.
- Lack of knowledge of how the strengths and limitations of alternative indicators for uses and outcomes of uses vary when applied in various contexts (different uses, different scales of space and time; different communities engaged in governance, etc.) {3.2.1.1}.
- There is much less information available on the governance of gathering and non-extractive uses compared to hunting, fishing and loggings {4.5}.
- An abundance of information about sustainable use of wild species is published and indexed in languages other than English. For example, there is an abundance of literature about gathered species of wild algae, fungi and plants in the Russian language literature. Lack of access to this information creates a gap in knowledge about uses of wild species that could be filled by resources dedicated to translating and analyzing that literature {3.5}.

Knowledge gaps and weaknesses in appropriate assessment or evaluation methods, including models, projection methods and scenarios

- There is a large knowledge gap on policy effectiveness. Few studies have rigorously evaluated the actual positive and negative outcomes of policies intended to promote the sustainability of the use of wild species. Rather, follow-up studies typically evaluate status of the use and the wild species, but not the effectiveness of the policies themselves for regulating use activities {5.6}.
- This gap is particularly apparent in wide-reaching policies and agreements like the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora; for most economic instruments; and for policies that address broad drivers, such as ones that address poverty alleviation; all of which can address known drivers of unsustainable practices but have diverse and sometimes unintended consequences and complex feedbacks {3.2.2, 6.5}.
- There are few robust scenarios that are suitable for exploration of potential options for maintaining or improving sustainability of uses, and for all uses available scenarios are rarely broad and integrative {5.3}. Current literature predominantly pertains to fisheries and logging, and predominately explores the impacts of climate change, or management interventions and their interactions with climate change. Other uses and themes are under-represented, particularly for non-business-as-usual scenarios {5.3}.

- For all practices almost no scenario explore cultural or equity aspects of use, nor the approaches of indigenous peoples and local communities. Scenarios rarely represent vulnerable groups who are dependent upon wild species, nor explore the intersection of broad top-down management and local governance in the context of equity {5.4, 5.6}.
- This knowledge gap on the evaluation of effectiveness of policies designed to support the sustainability of the use is particularly large for non-extractive practices such as nature-based tourism. Contributions of non-extractive uses to local community development may be assessed, but consequences for broader ecological impacts of use are rarely evaluated {6.5.2}.
- Social systems are complex, dynamic, and responsive to many factors. There is little documentation of how these social dynamics affect sustainable use; reciprocally of how the social dynamics may be caused or amplified by the status of species being used; and of how to address evolving understandings of equity, institutional arrangements, power dynamics, and values and norms in evaluations of effectiveness of sustainable use policies {4.5, 5.3, 6.7}.
- Knowledge gaps are especially large with respect to social norms, perceptions, and gendered dimensions of sustainable use overall, and particularly in the context of informal institutions and governance systems of indigenous peoples and local communities. These gaps are found around the globe but are especially apparent in Latin America and Asia {4.5}.
- For many species, the numerous potential drivers of unsustainable harvesting have not been examined fully enough to be able to partition causation and identify the role, if any, of specific environmental, economic and social factors when harvesting is excessive {4.5}.
- There are no globally accepted guidelines for assessing economic sustainability, nor an accepted definition nor quantitative metric(s) of what outcomes comprise economic sustainability, nor accepted approaches, nor agreed tools to facilitate comparisons of economic aspects of sustainability of use among different regions, uses, or specific cases {4.5}.
- There is very little study of the underlying dynamic relationships between language and biodiversity, including the roles of changes or differences in language in changing customs and practices affecting uses of wild species, and/or in changing expectations of outcomes that would be considered sustainable {4.5}.

Knowledge gaps about indigenous and local knowledge

- There is a dearth of formal documentation of the knowledge of indigenous peoples and local communities with regard to sustainable use of wild species. Consequently, coverage of these knowledge systems was not comparable to coverage of scientific sources {3.5, 4.5}.
- Methods to document indigenous and local knowledge and customary values, transfer that knowledge to scientific communities, and bridge that knowledge and those values with scientific information, are not yet widely used and would benefit from further exploration, development, and implementation {3.5, 4.5}.

- Although the loss of systems of indigenous and local knowledge is well documented, there has been little study of the processes and factors that drive the losses, the effects of the losses on society's capability to pursue sustainable use of wild species, nor of approaches to sustain traditional ecological knowledge systems {4.5}.
- There is a need to co-develop methods with indigenous peoples and local communities for weaving science and indigenous and local knowledge {3.5, 4.5}.
- There is a need to document indigenous and local knowledge regarding sustainable use of wild species, observing free, prior and informed consent {3.5}.
- There is a need to co-produce monitoring processes and indicators with indigenous peoples and local communities {3.5, 4.5}.
- There is a need to co-produce scenarios with indigenous peoples and local communities, based on indigenous and local knowledge and values {5.11}.
- There is a need to develop approaches to support and revitalize indigenous and local knowledge and customary governance {4.5}.
- There is a need to build capacity and support for indigenous peoples and local communities to conduct research, monitoring and governance to support and enhance the sustainability of the use of wild species {3.5, 4.5}.

Knowledge gaps about interactions of uses with other pressures and among multiple uses

- The various practices using wild species can interact ecologically, economically, and socially, and the potential for diverse tensions and synergies among uses are incompletely studied {3.4.3.3, 4.5, 5.4, 6.5}.
- The potential impact of climate change on the diverse range of wild species including underutilized species are only beginning to be assessed, and policies for the sustainability of the use are rarely tested for robustness in the face of climate change affecting the species and ecosystems being used {3.5, 4.5}.
- There is a gap in knowledge of the ecological impact of invasive alien species in ecosystems globally, particularly marine systems, and how such impacts affect sustainability of uses of native species {4.5}.
- There is limited information on the contribution of pollution and climate change to the global decline of wild species, impeding ability to provide options on effective interventions for all wild species, particularly for pollinating insects {4.5}.
- Many scenarios and projections jointly exploring environmental sustainability, biodiversity conservation, and climate change do not explicitly consider wild species use, particularly archetype scenarios corresponding to fortress worlds and inequality {5.4}.
- There needs to be a greater focus on sustainable use in the context of more integrated solutions to biodiversity loss, and consideration of how sustainable use interacts with conservation and other elements of a broadly sustainable society {5.4}.
- Urbanization can decrease human consumption of wild species. However, documentation is very patchy of how urbanization in lower income countries affects that consumption {4.5}.

- The knowledge gaps in how uses interact means there is an even larger gap in how policy instruments for one use affect opportunities for and performance of other uses; for example, how logging policies affect gathering and terrestrial animal harvesting {4.5, 6.5}; and a reciprocal gap in knowledge of how policies not developed to manage a specific use nevertheless can strongly influence opportunities and conduct of that use; for example, how policies for protection of non-harvested aquatic species can have large impacts on fisheries using target species sustainably {6.4.4.3}.

Knowledge gaps about economic, trade, and social value issues

- There is inadequate public understanding of the diverse social, including economic benefits provided by biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, and thus of the full value of conservation of biodiversity {3.4}.
- Particularly when applied to non-extractive uses, there has been limited research on the effectiveness of economic instruments such as tourism certification and visitation fees, and even less on other types of instruments {3.4.4.2, 5.4, 6.5}.
- There are few consistent standards and practices for collection of economic data, amplifying gaps in the availability of economic data on regional, national and subnational scales. Resultant inconsistencies in the official statistics and trade surveys for wild species lowers the robustness of evidence concerning outcomes, with particular shortcomings in official trade statistics that trace the status of threatened species {3.2}.
- Reliable data on local consumption and trade are frequently absent for food from wild species, particularly from butterflies, beetles, amphibians, reptiles and catches from recreational fishing {3.2.4, 3.5}.
- The value of wild species includes the social values of gathering and use of wild species in local markets, yet these values are rarely included in evaluations or planning {3.6.2.2, 3.6.2.4}.

Specific knowledge gaps – fishing, fish and fisheries

- There are regular assessments of status of fewer than half of fish stocks being harvested, with the assessment gap particularly large in much of South and East Asia, and Latin America {3.3.1.2}.
- Even where systematic monitoring, reporting, and status assessments occur, efforts may not be matched to the scales of harvesting and management. This is a particularly large gap for small-scale fisheries important in many coastal and inland areas {3.3.1.3.1, 3.3.1.3.3, 3.3.1.4.1}.
- In most fisheries, there are large gaps in understanding life histories of harvested species, making it hard to link information on other pressures on these populations to the information used in managing the fisheries {3.3.1.1}.
- Documentation of the impacts on non-target fish species from bycatch mortality and changes in status of harvested species that are ecologically associated or dependent is usually poor, and these impacts are rarely assessed {3.3.1.1, 3.3.1.3.5}.

- Available time series on population status and harvests of fished populations are often too short to allow impacts of fisheries to be disentangled from other causes of variation in population dynamics. Knowledge is particularly inadequate for long lived species of fish and marine mammals {3.3.1.1}.
- The global trade of marine ornamental fishes is not transparent and inadequately documented, with even origins of the fish in trade often not known {3.3.1.1, 3.3.1.5.2}.
- For fishing, projections of climate change impacts are relatively common, but the projections rarely explore climate impacts coupled with governance and equity considerations, and rarely consider freshwater systems or recreational fisheries {5.4}.

Specific knowledge gaps – gathering

- There is a knowledge gap on the extent of use and trade of medicinal plant species, particularly species with complex trade chains and high degree of processing, such as medicinal and aromatic products {3.3.2.1}, of their abundance in the areas where they are harvested, and of how the plants, particularly trees, respond to gathering methods {3.3.2.1, 3.3.2.3.5, 3.5}.
- Similar knowledge gaps exist for many wild plant species collected for human consumption, although locally the information available on plants used as food may be less incomplete than information for medicinal plants {3.3.2.2.2}.
- Few data are available for global trade in cut flowers from wild and managed habitats {3.3.2.3.2}.
- Gaps exist in *ex situ* conservation of plant species, for example in gene banks, in particular for wild crop relatives from tropical regions {3.3.2.3.5}.
- There is a knowledge gap on urban gathering, which is a particular concern for Asia and the Pacific region {3.3.2.2.2}.
- For gathering, limited data on production, trade volumes, and revenues impedes progress on addressing the overall lack of projections, scenarios, and evidence-based generalizations regarding gathering, although there are numerous limited studies on community-based management {5.4}.

Specific knowledge gaps – hunting, hunters, and species being hunted

- Few data are available on harvest of edible insects, whether for consumption by the harvester or for trade, and often not even the species or higher taxa being used is known {3.3.3.3.3, 3.5}.
- The information available on wild meat harvest is particularly incomplete in the Asian tropics and where hunting is not managed through licenses or comparable systems {3.2.1.3, 3.3.3.3.3}.
- More than 50% of traded reptiles lack species-specific identification, and often information on origins is insufficient to attribute specimens to a specific place of origin {3.3.3.3.3}.
- There is little information on how “green hunting” has changed hunting practices in the context of the sustainability of use of the species being hunted in new ways {3.3.3.4, 3.3.3.4.3}.

- For hunting, additional scenarios are needed to explore effects of environmental change, particularly climate-driven change, on hunting practices and outcomes, and the role of hunting, particularly trophy hunting, in conservation. Comparative studies may improve the evidence base and thereby the ability to generalize the limited findings available {5.4}.

Specific knowledge gaps – logging, loggers, and species being harvested

- Accurate identification of sources and even species of timber in trade is often not available, particularly for trade in the United States of America, Australia, and Europe {3.6.1.7}.
- Information is rarely sufficient to determine the relative amounts of timber which come from legal or illegal sources, particularly on larger scales of commerce; and in some markets it is not possible to differential timber from wild versus plantation sources {3.3.4.3.2}.
- Aside from high-income countries, even the number and species identity of the trees being harvested is poorly known, and it is not known which species are sought for harvest and which are harvested opportunistically {3.2.1.4}.
- For logging, as with fishing, there are a number of studies on climate change and sustainable use. However, most are fairly narrow and not sufficiently integrative to explore the interactions among climate change, development, biodiversity, and poverty, and how differing contextual factors such as biomes can affect these interactions {5.4}.

Specific knowledge gaps – nature-based tourism and wildlife watching

- With the exception of recreational tourism, there is extremely limited knowledge on the forms, trends or sustainability of non-extractive practices. The gap is particularly large for wild species used for decorative and aesthetic purposes {3.3.5.3.2, 3.5, 6.5}.
- There is little information on the impact of nature-based tourism on the less “charismatic” flora and fauna e.g., ground dwelling mammals, small reptiles, insects, plants without conspicuous flowers etc. {3.3.5.3.2}.
- For non-extractive practices, there are few scenario studies at all, and even fewer focused solely on non-extractive uses. There is also almost nothing on economic aspects of non-extractive uses beyond tourism {5.4.6}.
- There is a lack of longitudinal studies that assess the full scale of nature-based tourism’s social and ecological impacts {2.2.3.6.3}.